

THE IMPACT OF BIOFERTILIZERS ON THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF GENERATIVE AND VEGETATIVE ORGANS OF LEMON

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Introduction: The homeland of lemon is considered to be India, China, and the tropical islands of the Pacific, formed from the natural crossing of citrons and bitter oranges, and has developed as a distinct species over a long period. Each year, approximately 14 million tons of lemons are produced worldwide. The leading producing countries are India and Mexico, accounting for about 16% of the global yield. In Uzbekistan, 36,500 tons of lemons were produced in 2021. One of the key factors for obtaining a high-quality yield from fruit-bearing plants is timely fertilization. It is known that for many years, granular nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and various micronutrients have been widely used for the fertilization of fruit-bearing plants. The regular use of these macro-fertilizers is negatively affecting the meliorative condition of the soil in orchards.

The increase of various salt compounds in the soil, soil compaction, and the decrease or passiveness of resident microorganisms result in poor root system development in fruit-bearing plants, limiting their ability to assimilate nutrients adequately. Consequently, a range of negative effects can be observed, such as slow growth of fruit-bearing plants, increased susceptibility to diseases, lower resilience to environmental factors, and a sharp decline in yield. To prevent and partially eliminate these issues, it is crucial to use nitrogen-fixing microorganisms and biofertilizers that assimilate atmospheric molecular nitrogen (N_2) and convert it into organic compounds for fertilizing fruit-bearing plants. Such beneficial microorganisms are abundant in nature. The application of preparations made from nitrogen-fixing bacteria for the fertilization of fruit-bearing plants ensures the rapid growth and development of their vegetative and generative organs. Our scientific research during the cultivation of lemon plants using these biopreparations has yielded positive results.

Research Methods: Field experiments were conducted, analyzing the growth and developmental stages of the generative and vegetative organs of lemon plants, conducting phenological observations, and analyzing and evaluating biometric measurements based on the methodology by Kh. Ch.

Buryiev and others, titled “Methods of Calculating and Conducting Phenological Observations in Experiments with Fruit and Berry Plants” (2014).

Research Results: Timely and adequate application of various macro and micro fertilizers, maintaining proper irrigation, optimal moisture, temperature, and light conditions can lead to high-quality yields. It is known that lemon is a small tree with dense green leaves that blooms for an extended period. Additionally, its flowers and fruits are fragrant. With proper care, an average of 10-12 fruits can be harvested from a 3-5 year old tree. For optimal fertilization, it is essential to consider the plant's needs; otherwise, the lack of nutrients can signal problems, manifesting in flower and ovary formation issues. If no measures are taken, the plant may perish.

Irrigation with established water can bring benefits, as it allows for root system hydration and contributes to the healthy development of the yield. However, it can also wash away nutrients. Thus, obtaining a high-quality yield without fertilizers is challenging.

In natural conditions, the root system of a lemon tree is approximately 30-40 times larger than that in a container, allowing it to access nutrients from deeper soil layers. Fertilizing lemon with appropriate fertilizers helps bridge this gap.

Knowing which fertilizers are needed for lemon can prevent potential problems. Weak growth and poor flowering may require the use of nitrogen-rich preparations for reinforcement. Signs of nitrogen deficiency include slow growth, yellowing leaves, and poorly developed buds. If growth is rapid but flowering is poor, this may indicate a phosphorus deficiency, which first impacts flowering and fruiting. Additionally, citrus fruits may exhibit leaf drop and discoloration.

Potassium deficiency manifests as yellowing edges of leaves, eventually leading to chlorosis and delayed fruit ripening, resulting in soft lemons. If the tops of young lemon tree shoots begin to die, immediate calcium supplementation is required. Deficiencies can also affect the root system. Besides essential nutrients, plants may also suffer from micronutrient deficiencies. The most common issue is iron deficiency, which manifests as chlorosis. This is evident in the formation of light spots in the interveinal spaces. Once affected tissues die, leaves will drop.

Nitrogen-Fixing Fertilizers: The best fertilizers for lemons today are those that meet specific nutrient requirements. Nitrogenous fertilizers are essential for the active growth of leaves, dense stems, and proper ovary formation. Nitrogen also helps prevent slow growth, yellowing leaves, poor flowering, and fruit drop.

Phosphorus-Containing Fertilizers: Phosphorus-containing fertilizers are necessary for the proper development of fruit. This element allows lemon trees to grow beautifully and prevents coarse, thick skins. Phosphorus also helps prevent leaf yellowing and drop.

Potassium-Containing Fertilizers: Potassium fertilizers are essential to prevent the appearance of yellow and light spots on the leaves. In citrus trees, the absence of potassium can lead to sap exudation on the leaf surface. Prolonged deficiency can result in total leaf loss and plant death. Understanding the necessary fertilizers for lemons makes it easier to avoid negative outcomes. It is recommended to use not only nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium but also a variety of micronutrients necessary for the proper development of the tree. Such fertilizers should be applied from the beginning of May to the end of October. Mineral fertilizers can be alternated with organic fertilizers. An effective mixture can be prepared from bird droppings: take 1 part droppings to 9 parts slightly heated water. Under no circumstances should you fertilize dry soil; it is essential to moisten it first. The nutrient solution should be applied in small portions until the soil is completely saturated. The temperature of the solution must match that of the soil mixture in the lemon container.

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